

OPTIMIZATION OF THE RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING PROCESS FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITES

Anders Strömbeck
Swedish Institute of Composites
Box 271
S-941 26 Piteå, Sweden

ABSTRACT

A new injection strategy is proposed which substantially reduces the mould fill time in RTM. In addition the new method provides possibilities to control the resin flow pattern and thus avoid air inclusions. The proposed injection strategy has been experimentally verified for a pipelike structure with a glass content of 55 % by volume and also for a geometrically complex part. Comparisons with theoretical calculations for conventional injection strategies show a substantial reduction of mould fill time.

Keywords: Resin transfer moulding, Process optimization, Mould filling, Injection strategies.

1. INTRODUCTION

RTM has the potential to become an efficient production method for advanced fibre composite parts. The process is flexible in terms of geometrical shape of components and choice of resin and reinforcement materials. Moreover, significant advantages of the process are the abilities to control fibre orientation, incorporate cores/inserts into the composite part and to obtain a low laminate void content [1]. The RTM process can be divided into three main steps: placement of reinforcement, mould filling and resin cure. These steps have to be optimized and fully controlled to obtain high quality products and a cost efficient process.

In the present study the RTM process has been investigated for the production of load bearing composite parts. The main goal has been to secure part quality by optimisation of the mould filling. Two experimental moulds have been constructed for laboratory tests, one having a tubular shaped mould cavity and the second having a more complex geometry. A special feature of the experimental moulds is that the two moulds can be connected thus forming a new mould with a cavity which is a combination of the two separate moulds. This combined mould makes parts having the complexities of a boat rudder with an integrated rudder stock.

The mould filling of an advanced composite part is a main problem since no air inclusion can be accepted. In this paper a new injection strategy is presented which have several advantages compared to conventional injection. The new injection principle is shown to reduce mould fill time and to provide possibilities for control of the mould filling in such a way that air inclusion is avoided.

2. THEORY

2.1 Mould filling calculations

The theory of mould filling has been studied quite extensively in recent years. It is well proven that Darcy's law, equation (1), can describe the flow of resins in fibre preforms accurately for modelling purposes [2,3]. Darcy's law describes the flow of Newtonian fluids in porous media and it states that the volumetric flow rate through a constant area specimen is proportional to the cross section area, pressure difference over the specimen and inversely proportional to the length in the streamwise direction and the fluid viscosity. A constant included in the model, termed permeability, is only a function of the reinforcements geometry. Equation (2) is Darcy's law rewritten for the flow front velocity, u .

$$\frac{Q}{A} = \frac{K \Delta p}{\mu L} \quad (1)$$

$$u = \frac{K \Delta p}{\mu L} \frac{1}{1-V_f} \quad (2)$$

Integration of Darcy's law with the assumption that the pressure at a reference point (the beginning of the reinforcement in the mould), the permeability in the streamwise direction and the fibre volume fraction is constant yields:

$$x_f^2 = 2 \frac{K}{\mu} \frac{\Delta p}{(1-V_f)} t \quad (3)$$

where x_f is the flow front position measured from the reference point where the pressure is measured, t is the time, Δp is the pressure drop from the reference point to the flow front where atmospheric pressure is present, μ is the viscosity and where V_f is the fibre volume fraction. Equation (3) is valid provided that an additional pressure drop from the air flow through the reinforcement in front of the resin and effects from surface tension at the flow front can be neglected.

The time for mould filling through a constant area of any distance can easily be calculated with equation (3) provided that the resin viscosity, the reinforcement permeability, the fibre volume fraction and the injection pressure are known. Such data can easily be obtained except for the permeability of which useful values for commercial reinforcements are scarce. However, it is quite easy to measure the permeability [4]. Permeability values used in this work has been obtained from published data [5].

2.3 Void formation

It is of high importance that the laminate void content is low in several composite applications. Recent studies have shown that the use of vacuum inside the mould during mould filling in RTM is an efficient way of reducing the void content [6, 7]. These recent studies has also found strong indications of mechanisms for void formation and void mobility in reinforcements. The implication of this is that vacuum assistance during mould filling is important for the reduction of void content and also for the extent of the void region in RTM.

2.2 Injection strategies

The choice of injection strategy is important since it will affect both the flow pattern and the injection time. There are several different strategies in use and described in the literature[8, 9]. Point injection refers to when the inlet point is placed close to the center of the mould cavity and air is vented at the edges. Another way of injection is to provide the mould with a resin distribution

channel along one side of the mould cavity thus forming a wide flow front propagating towards the opposite side where air is vented. A third injection strategy is termed peripheral injection and refers to when a resin distribution channel runs around all edges of the part and the resin flow will propagate from all sides towards the center where air is vented. It has been shown both experimentally and theoretically that peripheral injection is faster than edge injection which in turn is faster than point injection [9]. Time factors of about ten have been reported comparing peripheral and point injection.

The injection time for all strategies above can be speeded up by adding additional inlet points. A sequential multiple port injection has been proposed and shown by numerical calculations to reduce mould fill time[10]. This strategy is based on a sequential scheme of resin supply to inlet points placed along the direction of the global front. The use of sequential multiple ports for injection can reduce fill time substantially.

A new injection strategy is presented here which in theory will reduce the fill time to a minimum without an increase in void content. Furthermore it provides possibilities to avoid air inclusions in complex mould geometries. The principle for this strategy is shown in Figure 1 which shows a cross section of a mould. The mould cavity in Figure 1 is chosen to be of cylindrical shape thus producing straight pipe parts which simplifies an illustration and analysis of the injection strategy. The principle is to inject the resin through a resin channel and to control the resin flow front by a movable piston. The inside walls of the resin channel is made up of a liner material which the resin can permeate easily in the radial direction. By moving the piston in the direction of flow in such a way that the distance(x in Figure 1) between the piston face and the flow front is constant results in a constant pressure gradient in the region behind the moving flow front and hence a constant flow rate throughout the mould filling of the part providing the resin pressure is constant close to the piston. The distance x between the resin flow front and the end of the piston depends on the rate of advancement of the piston.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Objectives

The objective of the experimental study is to verify the applicability of the new injection strategy for both cylindrical parts as well as for more complex parts. Two experimental moulds have been constructed and built for the investigation.

3.2 Materials and equipment

Mould 1 has a cavity which has the shape of a tube with a diameter of 46.9 mm and a length of 970 mm. The lower mould half is made of aluminum and the upper half is made of transparent PMMA to make observations of the flow possible. The mould halves are kept together with bolts evenly spaced. All injection points and vents are placed in end plugs which can be mounted on any of the two ends of the mould.

Mould 2 has a cavity shaped roughly as a rudder i. e. varying thickness and nonsymmetrical in one plane. A sketch of Mould 2 is shown in Figure 2. The maximum width and length of the cavity are 450 mm and 250 mm respectively and the thickness varies from 61.5 mm to 41.5 mm. Mould 2 is made of the same materials as Mould 1 and is in principle of the same construction with end plugs positioned at two opposite sides for injection and venting points. These end plugs can be replaced by a special fitting which makes it possible to connect Mould 1 and 2 and form a new mould cavity which is a combination of the two moulds.

The experimental injections were made with a pressure pot in which a beaker of precatalyzed resin was placed. The resin was pressurized in the pot and transferred to the inlet gate in the mould via a dip tube. The injection pressures mentioned in the experimental part refers to the pressure applied to the pressure pot.

A vinyl ester resin (BASF Palatal A 430-01) has been used in all experiments. Type and concentrations of catalyst components was chosen for a geltime of about 25 minutes at room temperature. The resin viscosity was measured to be 0.5 Pas at 25° C.

The following glass fibre reinforcements have been used in the experiments:

A. Brochier Lyvertex 21130, unidirectional glass weave, surface weight= 440 g/m²

B. Brochier glass weave E 3193, surface weight=400 g/m²

C. Vetrotex CSM Unifilo 812, surface weight= 450 g/m²

3.3. Experimental procedures

3.3.1. Injection #1 in Mould 1

A preform was made with reinforcement A by winding the weave tightly onto a perforated liner with the unidirectional fibres placed in 90° related to the axial direction of the liner tube. The liner was prepared from a polypropylene tube by drilling a large number of small holes equally spaced circumferentially and along the whole length of the tube. The outer diameter of the liner was 40.4 mm and the laminate thickness, defined by the liner and mould cavity diameter, was 3.25 mm. The volume fraction of fibres was calculated to be 55 %. A rod of PTFE polymer fitted with a firm seal was used as a piston which was placed in the liner and filled the whole space inside the liner at the starting point of injection. Resin was supplied from a pressure pot, at room temperature, with a constant pressure of 0.2 MPa to the inlet point placed at one side of the mould. The inlet point was positioned so the resin enters the mould at the inside of the liner. The injection was done by controlling the piston position in such a way that the distance between the piston face and the flow front position was about 20 mm during the whole mould filling. This distance could be controlled through observation of the moving flow front in the mould and by manual adjustment of the piston which was provided with marks outside of the mould to track the piston face position. The time for the whole injection of the 970 mm long tube was 14 minutes.

3.3.2. Injection #2 in Mould 1+2.

A complex preform was made having the principal geometry of a rudder including a rudder stock. A picture of an almost completed preform is shown in Figure 3. The rudder stock of the preform was constructed by the same method as outlined above for injection #1 and has a length of 1400 mm of which 400 mm protrudes into the rudder blade. The laminate thickness of the rudder stock was 3.25 mm with a fibre volume fraction of about 30 %. The rudder blade was made up from two pieces of accurately shaped foam core material which was fitted closely to the preform stock and wrapped with a weave reinforcement in precut pieces so the amount of reinforcement was quite evenly distributed along and enclosing the blade surfaces. Reinforcement B was used both for the stock and the blade. In addition a piece of continuous strand mat (reinforcement C) was put on both sides of the blade to make sure that the whole surface of the blade should have good contact with the mould. The outer surface of the preform stock was wrapped with a surface cloth which completed the preform. The laminate thickness of the blade skin was about 4 mm and the fibre volume fraction was about 25 %.

Mould 1 and 2 were connected and formed a mould into which the preform was placed. Special care was taken not to squeeze the fibre preform edges at the mould seal faces during mould closing. The resin inlet point was placed at the far end of the cylindrical part of the combined mould. Injection was done following the principles outlined above for injection #1 with the exception of the distance between the piston face and the resin flow front which was kept at about 40 mm for injection #2. The pressure was kept constant at 0.2 MPa in the pressure pot during injection. Figure 4 is a picture taken during mould filling at the point where the impregnation of the axial part is completed and the resin flow front is propagating in to the blade part of the preform. The time for the whole injection of the 1400 mm long part was 14.5 minutes.

4. RESULTS

The mould fill times for the experimental injection tests are summarised in Table 1. Visual observations of the injections in the moulds revealed a remarkably stable resin front also in the

experiment with a quite complex sandwich preform(Injection #2). Resin leakage at the reinforcement edges, which often causes severe problems with entrapment of air at unwanted positions in the mould, was negligible. Examination of the parts after cure and demoulding showed no visible air inclusions. However, the surfaces of the cured parts were rough most probably due to resin shrinkage.

Table 1. Experimental fill times for injection #1 and #2.

Injection	Fill time, minutes	
	Mould 1	Mould 1+2
#1	14	-
#2	9.5	14.5

Calculated fill times for different injection strategies in Mould 1 is shown in Table 2. Equation (3) has been used to calculate the fill time of a conventional injection with one inlet point i.e. the fill time for a constant cross-sectional area specimen of length L with the assumption of a constant resin pressure throughout the cross-sectional area at the beginning of the preform close to the inlet point. The calculation of fill time for the new injection principle, corresponding to experimental injection #1, has been done by assuming a constant distance, $x = 20$ mm (see figure 1), between the moving flow front and the piston face and a constant resin pressure close to the piston under the whole course of injection. The assumption above implies a constant flow velocity which is calculated with equation (2), assuming Darcy's law is valid. Thus the time for mould filling can easily be calculated for any length L. The following data which corresponds with experimental injection #1, have been used in the calculations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_f &= 55 && \% \\
 \Delta p &= 0.2 && \text{MPa} \\
 \mu &= 0.5 && \text{Pas} \\
 L &= 0.970 && \text{m} \\
 K &= 2 * 10^{-11} && \text{m}^2 \text{ (from [4])}
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 2. Comparison of calculated fill times for two different injection strategies.

Injection strategy	Fill time, minutes
Conventional	880
New	18

5. CONCLUSION

A new injection strategy is proposed and is shown to substantially reduce mould fill time compared to conventional injection techniques. Furthermore, this strategy provides possibilities to control mould flow pattern in such a way that air inclusions can be avoided. The experimental results indicates that the proposed method of injection can be used successfully for the manufacturing of parts with a high fibre volume fraction and also of parts with geometrical complexities.

The described method of injection has some obvious restrictions and drawbacks such as a resin channel must be present in the interior of the preform which will either be filled with neat resin or cleared by a suggested return of the piston at the end of mould filling and thus cause resin waste. However, it is as well obvious that the method is suited for composite parts designed with a hollow interior such as pipes or for components for which a short injection time is of high importance. The use of vacuum assistance is needed, if product demands on void content is critical, for the proposed

injection method since resin flow is limited to short distances in the reinforcement and entrapped voids may not escape to the resin flow front.

Acknowledgements

Mr Erik Sandlund, a member of the RTM research group at SICOMP, has been taking an active part in this project for exploring RTM process technology. He has been responsible for the main parts of the experimental activities and has supported the project with a great number of new ideas of which several have been invaluable for the realization of the experimental plan.

References

1. Hansen, R.S., *RTM Processing and Applications*, SME Technical Paper EM90-214, 1990.
2. Fracchia, C.A. and C.L. Tucker III. *Simulation of Resin Transfer Mould Filling*, Presented at the 6th Annual Meeting, Nice, France, Polymer Processing Society. 1990.
3. Gebart, B.R., *Permeability of unidirectional Reinforcements for RTM*, Journal of Composite Materials, 26, 1992, pp.1100-1133.
4. Lidström, P., *Measurement of In-plane Permeability of Anisotropic Media*, M.Sc. Thesis, Luleå University of Technology, Sweden, 1992.
5. Gebart, B.R., Peter Gudmundson, L.A. Strömbeck and C.Y. Lundemo, *Analysis of the Permeability in RTM Reinforcements*, Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Composite Materials, 15-E, Honolulu, USA, 1991.
6. Hayward, J.S. and Harris, B., *The Effect of Vacuum Assistance in Resin Transfer Moulding*, *Composites Manufacturing*, 1, pp 161-166, 1990.
7. Lundström, T.S. and B.R. Gebart. *Influence from Different Process Parameters on Void Formation in Resin Transfer Moulding*, Submitted to Polymer Composites. 1993.
8. Gehrig, H. *Gegenüberstellung verschiedener Varianten des Harz-injektionsverfahrens zur herstellung von GF-UP-Formteilen*. Plasverarbeiter, Heft 2, 1981.
9. Gebart, B.R., C.Y. Lundemo and Peter Gudmundson. *An Evaluation of Alternative Injection Strategies in RTM*. Proceedings of the 47th Annual Conference of the Society of Plastics Institute, Cincinnati, USA, 1992.
10. Chan, A.W. and R.J. Morgan. *Sequential Multiple Port Injection for Resin Transfer Molding of Polymer Composites*, SAMPE Quarterly, Vol 24, No 1, pp. 45-49, 1992.

Figure 1. Sketch of cut section in a principle mould for a new injection strategy.
 1. Interior resin channel. 2. Permeable inside liner. 3. Piston. 4. Resin inlet gate.
 5. Seals for piston exit hole. 'x' is the distance between the moving resin flow front and the piston face.

Figure 2. Sketch of Mould 2.

Figure 3. Picture of an almost completed preform made up of glass weaves. The geometry of the preform is similar to a boat rudder including the rudder stock. The overall length is 1500 mm and maximum width is 400 mm. The 'rudder' blade is a sandwich construction with a skin thickness of about 4 mm.

Figure 4. Picture showing mould filling of a complex preform with a new injection strategy. The upper mould half is made of PMMA which makes observation of mould interior possible. The flow front moves from the right to the left in the picture.